

Publication of ESPCE - related citizen
science data and graphical maps in the
citizen science interface

Date: 14.5.2025

Doc. Version: V1

doi: [10.5281/zenodo.18242976](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18242976)

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Deliverable Title	Publication of ESPCE - related citizen science data and graphical maps in the citizen science interface
Work Package Title	Synergies with ESPCE
Deliverable number	D12.2
Description	Report on the publication of citizen science data related to the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (ESPCE) which were collected during the citizen campaigns of Task 12.2. The data are published in the citizen science interface (project portal). Graphs and maps indicating locations and respective quantities/frequencies of plastic litter data have been produced.
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Submitted by	Eva Chatzinikolaou (HCMR-IMBBC)
Doc. Version (Revision number)	V1
Sensitivity (Security):	Public
Date:	8/6/2025

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date
Antonio Novellino	WP9 Leader	Revision and approved	22/5/2025

Document history:

The Document Author is authorized to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarized in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
V1	14/05/2025	Eva Chatzinikolaou	First draft
V2	07/06/2025	Eva Chatzinikolaou	Final draft

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in <location>.

Nature of the deliverable		
R	Report	✓
DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator	
O	Other	
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot	

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

● ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This report forms part of the deliverables from the NAUTILOS project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000825. The Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of the content of this publication.

NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.NAUTILOS-h2020.eu/>.

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I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Objectives of this deliverable

The increasing amount of plastic litter poses a threat for the marine environment, biodiversity and human health. The current lifecycle of plastics—from design and production to use and disposal—has harmful consequences for our society, economy, and environment. The European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (ESCPe)¹ takes an ambitious stance on improving the recyclability of plastic packaging and includes robust measures to also address microplastics as a major contributor to marine pollution.

The main objective of Task 12.2 is to raise awareness for marine plastic pollution and offer knowledge to students and the general public, willing to act as citizen scientists and participate actively in the monitoring and elimination of plastics. The Citizen Science (CS) activities that have been performed within Task 12.2 are specifically focused on plastic pollution and on the implementation of the ESCPE. These activities are complementary to the CS activities performed in WP10 (Task 10.4), which include activities focused on biodiversity and ocean monitoring and are described in D10.9².

The protocols, methods and further organisational and implementation aspects of the CS activities performed within Task 12.2 are extensively described in deliverable D12.3. The present deliverable D12.2 aims to describe the processes followed for the organization and publication of the ESPCE-related Citizen Science data, as well as the development of graphical maps and reports produced within the citizen science interface of the project. The plastic pollution data collected following the CS campaigns include georeferenced locations and respective quantities of plastic litter for different litter categories.

1.2. Area of focus

The deliverable D12.2 supports the implementation of the SO7 as described in the Grant Agreement of the NAUTILOS project, which is relevant to the appropriate processes followed to ensure that the data produced by the project are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). One of the targets of NAUTILOS is the development of an end-to-end information system and infrastructure for both data management and data transfer towards well-established repository services. Therefore, the publication of the CS data to the established NAUTILOS project data portal, as well as to additional open access databases such as EMODnet, signifies their importance and potential for wider impact.

The main target audience of this Task includes school students (primary and secondary education), university students and early career scientists, researchers, maritime professionals and fishermen, local and regional authorities, citizen's associations, and the general public.

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1516265440535&uri=COM:2018:28:FIN>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/14856149>

II. COLLECTION OF PLASTIC LITTER DATA BY CITIZENS SCIENTISTS

Citizen Science (CS) activities have been organized in Crete (Greece) by HCMR-IMBBC during which students of primary and secondary education, as well as the general public, participated in beach cleaning campaigns for the collection and classification of plastic litter. These activities are described in detail in Deliverable D12.3 which is currently under preparation. A total of 24 beach campaigns were organized in 9 different locations and during a total period of 36 months (May 2022 – May 2025). A total number of 923 participants (mainly students) were actively involved in the CS campaigns and collected 20,405 items of plastic litter (Table 1, Figure 1).

Table 1. Beach cleaning campaigns organized in Crete for the collection of plastic litter data by Citizen Scientists.

School	Location	Dates	Grade	Participants	Age	Plastic Items
Primary school Limenas Chersonissou	Aposelemis, Arina	23/5/2022, 7/6/2022	3 rd , 5 th , 6 th	74	8-12	1476 1897
Primary school Elias	Camps Kokkini Chani	26/5/2022	1 st , 2 nd , 5 th	53	6-11	262
Primary school Gournon	Aquarium	6/6/2022	2 nd	24	7-8	1221
12 th High School of Heraklion & Erasmus+ project (Poland, Romania, Spain, Turkey, Portugal)	Arina	11/10/2022	2 nd , 3 rd	40	13-15	1839
Primary school Gouvon	Aquarium	20/10/2022	4 th	38	9-10	1269
Primary school Elias	Aquarium	26/10/2022	2 nd	19	7-8	666
Primary school Neas Alikarnassou	Gazi	3/3/2023	2 nd	32	7-8	373
Special Primary School of Heraklion (hearing loss)	Aquarium	16/3/2023	3 rd , 6 th	12	8-12	277
High School of Tylisos	Aquarium	4/4/2023	3 rd	22	14-15	271
Art Lyceum	Aquarium	8/5/2023	1 st , 2 nd	50	15-17	1044
47 th Primary School of Heraklion	Karteros	12/5/2023	5 th	50	10-11	1568
Elia Primary School	Aquarium	24/11/2023	6 th	24	11-12	880
45 th Primary School of Heraklion & 3rd Special Primary School	Aquarium	30/11/2023	2 nd	65	7-8	243
Gouves Primary School	Aquarium	5/4/2024	5 th	38	10-11	503
NAUTILOS summer school	Aquarium	18/4/2024		20	20-30	438
Citizens group ATAXTOI	Xeropotamos	21/4/2024		30	6-40	893
40 th Primary School of Heraklion	Xeropotamos	20/5/2024	6 th	30	11-12	541
43 rd Primary School of Heraklion	Xeropotamos	20/5/2024	2 nd	40	7-8	433
Elia Primary School	Aquarium	22/5/2024	1 st , 2 nd	45	6-8	399
47 th Primary School of Heraklion	Aquarium	6/6/2024	5 th , 6 th	45	10-12	475
2 nd Malia Primary school	Potamos	22/11/2024	4 th , 5 th	40	9-11	863
Souda Lyceum	Vlites	19/1/2025	1 st	46	15-16	892
13 rd High School of Heraklion	Aquarium	11/3/2025	1 st , 2 nd	46	12-14	1111
1 st Primary School of Agios Nikolaos	Aquarium	7/5/2025	5 th	40	10-11	571
9 locations		36 months		923 people		20,405 items plastic litter

Figure 1. Beach cleaning campaigns organized in Crete for the collection of plastic litter data by Citizen Scientists.

The plastic waste collected during those voluntary campaigns has been recorded as different types of plastic litter categories according to the EMODnet Chemistry Thematic Lot n°4 categories (J code List)³. The selected categories were simplified in order to be offered as a user-friendly laminated form translated both in Greek and English, as shown in Figure 2. Additional information collected during the campaigns included the following metadata:

- code of the campaign
- date
- beach name
- location
- coordinates (mandatory field)
- name of the contributors (i.e. school name)
- length and width of the beach
- surrounding type (cliffs, dunes, rocks, forest, bush, crops, fields, built up area, road)
- sediment type (mud, sand, coarse sediment, mixed sediment, rock and boulders)
- adverse weather conditions (wind, rain, snow, ice, fog, sand storm, exceptionally high tide)

The users had also the opportunity to enrich their dataset by adding a representative image that could be acquired directly from the camera or picked from the device's gallery.

³ https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/bitstream/handle/11329/1522.4/Guidelines-Litter_Data_v7_1.pdf?sequence=6&isAllowed=y

Recording plastics on the beach

Date:
 Beach name:
 Area:
 Coordinates:
 Participants (number):
 Age:
 School:
 Grade:

Type	Number
Plastic bags	
Plastic bottles (e.g. water, soft drinks, milk)	
Plastic containers - bottles (e.g. detergents)	
Bottle caps	
Plastic cups	
Plastic cups lids	
Bottle rings	
Gloves	
Lighters	

Type	Number
Straws	
Cigarette butts	
Pens	
Food packaging (e.g. chips)	
Single use cutlery	
Single use dishes	
Ear swabs	
Nets and ropes	
Fishing lines	
Plastic Buckets and Large Containers	
Styrofoam	
Surgical masks	
Other plastics (undefined)	

Figure 2. The laminated form offered to Citizen Scientists for the collection of data during the beach cleaning campaigns.

III. DATA PORTAL AND THE CITIZEN SCIENCE APPLICATION

All the plastic litter data have been uploaded to the NAUTILOS Data Portal⁴ as the layer “CS-Plastic” (Figure 3) through the Citizen Science Application (CS App)⁵ that was created to serve all the Citizen Science campaigns of the project. The Data portal and the CS App are described in detail in deliverables D8.7⁶ and D8.8⁷, which are available in project’s website.

⁴ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/data-portal/>

⁵ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/nautilus-cs-app/>

⁶ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/NAUTILOS-D8.7-Fully-developed-Graphic-User-Interface.pdf>

⁷ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/NAUTILOS-D8.8-Citizen-Science-tools-and-interface.pdf>

Figure 3. NAUTILOS portal and the data layer for plastic litter collected by Citizen Scientists.

The primary goal of the developed CS App is to support citizen science activities that NAUTILOS project partners and other ocean-related professional organizations can perform. The CS App (Figure 4) is a tool that has been designed, implemented, and integrated into the NAUTILOS data infrastructure. Through it, the acquired data are exported to the NAUTILOS ERDDAP data server, which supports sharing of data collection in a standardised way and guarantees straightforward access to the collected scientific data. The CS App allows for the uploading and analyzing of data gathered during the various Citizen Science campaigns. Data acquisition, management, and visualization work as a common entry-point to operate as a bridge towards NAUTILOS data infrastructure, with which they are fully integrated.

Figure 4. The NAUTILOS Citizen Science Application. The fields required for creating a new CS campaign for plastic litter are shown (middle), as well as the menu (right) for selecting a stored campaign in order to upload the CS data.

The CS App has been developed in order to facilitate the real-time collection of data on the beach and also to give the users the option to upload their data at a later time when a connection will be available. Entering of data is easy and efficient since the metadata and data fields of the campaign-form are similar with the data entry fields of the App. The App allows either automatic GPS positioning or manual insertion of a close-by position after which each new data entry will appear as pin on the map. The CS App is available for download after filling out a contact form⁸ and receiving an approved registration (Figure 5). In addition, a detailed CS App User Guide⁹ is available.

The screenshot shows a web page titled 'CONTACT US'. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: Home, The Project, Partners, Demonstrations, Citizen Science, Results, News, Resources, and Contact. Below the navigation, the 'CONTACT US' title is centered. The form consists of three input fields: 'Name', 'Email', and 'Message'. The 'Message' field is a larger text area. A 'Submit' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 5. Contact form to request access to the CS App.

The CS App is also available as a web browser version¹⁰ (Figure 6). This web CS App provides the users with an alternative tool to upload and share their data in the NAUTILOS portal, also at a later time following the end of each field campaign. Besides being natively connected with the NAUTILOS ERDDAP data server, the web CS App extends the mobile CS App features by offering advanced data editing functionalities and includes a fully described data collection. The browser version shares a similar interface and structure with the smartphone application to ease the passage between the applications (Figures 6, 7 and 8). The use of these two tools as a data collection workflow (i.e. mob App on field and web App after the end of each campaign mission) enhances their usability and the overall user experience during the campaign, and furthermore it offers a secure and safe methodology to complete, correct and update key metadata for FAIRness compliance.

Figure 6. Home page of the web browser version of the CS App.

⁸ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/contact/>

⁹ https://nautilus-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/CS-App-guide_NAUTILOS.pdf

¹⁰ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/desktop-app/>

Figure 7. The web browser version of the CS App – selection of the “Plastic Campaigns” scenario.

Figure 8. The web browser version of the CS App – Map page.

In addition to the functionalities available in the smartphone application, from the web browser version the users can edit the data reports that have been already shared into the NAUTILOS ERDDAP data server. A dedicated page (Figure 9) displays the list of sent reports along with the relevant edit buttons. A modal will be shown with all the data previously inserted; the user can modify them and submit again to the ERDDAP data server.

Edit reports

Plastics			
Campaign Name	Date	Uid	Operation
Crete_Aquarium_Apr2024	2024-04-05	6	Edit Image
Crete_Aquarium_April2023	2023-04-04T10:10:57	6	Edit Image
Crete_Aquarium_June2024	2024-06-06	6	Edit Image
Crete_Potamos_November2024	2024-11-22	6	Edit Image
Crete_Xeropotamos_May2024	2024-05-20	6	Edit Image
Nautilos Summer School	2024-04-18	6	Edit Litter Edit Image
New Test	2025-04-30	1	Edit Campaign Edit Litter
Test	2025-03-28	1	Edit Campaign Edit Litter Edit Image

Figure 9. Edit reports functionality in the web browser version of the CS App.

IV. PUBLICATION OF CITIZEN SCIENCE PLASTIC LITTER DATA IN EMODNET CHEMISTRY DATABASE

The data of plastic litter collected during the Citizen Science campaigns that were implemented in Crete (Greece) during the project were archived according to EMODnet Chemistry Thematic Lot n°4 categories (J code List)¹¹. Data from 12 beach cleaning campaigns (May 2022 – May 2023) were organized as the first “NAUTILOS – Citizen Science Plastic Litter” data batch and were submitted to EMODnet (November 2023). The collection was accepted on 8th April 2024 and is now included in EMODnet catalogue¹² (Figure 10). The following 8 beach cleaning campaigns in Crete (May 2023 – May 2024) produced the second NAUTILOS CS data batch that was submitted to EMODnet (October 2024) following the same procedure and has been also published (28th May 2025)¹³. All data have been published with no limitations to public access under a CC-BY 4.0 license. A new submission (June 2025) includes plastic litter data from the last 4 CS campaigns (May 2024 – May 2025) and is pending for publication.

Data on beach plastic litter have a high value, are of interest for many stakeholders and are largely used by marine scientists, policymakers, local authorities and environmental agencies across Europe and beyond. Offering updated marine plastic litter data, under the FAIR principles and fully accessible in the NAUTILOS data portal and in the EMODnet catalogue, supports the implementation of several

¹¹https://repository.oceanbestpractices.org/bitstream/handle/11329/1522.4/Guidelines-Litter_Data_v7_1.pdf?sequence=6&isAllowed=y

¹²<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/61ab1504-dc02-4685-b3e9-1748cf439358>

¹³<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/dd7f5d48-7eca-45cb-9980-5240b3c72399>

relevant EU Directives and guarantees that they will be discoverable, securely stored and accessible over the long-term.

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Export metadata

Modalità di visualizzazione

NAUTILOS - Citizen Science Plastic Litter Crete 2022-2023

This dataset includes data of plastic litter collected by citizens and students during 12 campaigns that were organised in Crete (Greece) during the period May 2022 – May 2023. The campaigns were organized within the framework of the NAUTILOS Horizon 2020 project. More specifically the number of plastic litter items per category (using the J code List of the EMODnet Chemistry Thematic Lot n°4) was recorded together with information about the location, date, surface area covered, data contributor and some environmental characteristics (sediment, weather, surroundings).

Estensione temporale
2022-05-23 → 2023-05-12

Discover data

Export metadata

<https://cloud.emodnet-ingestion.eu/index.php/s/NIZIGYu2TYf7DWA>

Scaricare

Formato

Delimited

Figure 10. The NAUTILOS Citizen Science data for plastic litter in Cretan beaches (May 2022 – May 2023) have been published in EMODnet catalogue.

V. VISUALISATION TOOLS FOR CS PLASTIC LITTER DATA

The primary point of access for NAUTILOS data is the NAUTILOS web data portal (see Deliverable D8.7¹⁴ for a comprehensive description). The NAUTILOS web portal interface was designed to match end-user requirements. It implements a WebGIS viewer and provides an explorable digital map based on layers displaying different types of data. Data related to plastic pollution include the plastic litter data collected during Citizen Science beach cleaning campaigns (section II) (Figure 11), the data collected by commercial fishing vessels participating in AdriFOOS (section VI), the Marine Litter Trackers data (section VII) and the drone monitoring litter data (section VIII).

¹⁴ <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/NAUTILOS-D8.7-Fully-developed-Graphic-User-Interface.pdf>

Figure 11. Explorable digital map with the plastic litter data collected during Citizen Science beach cleaning campaigns.

The users are able to select, combine and display the different CS datasets and their metadata as separate map layers. The available layers can be activated through the Layers Controller placed in the top right corner of the map. When loaded, the data are displayed as clusters (circles with the number of contained markers in their center) which open up as independent points when the user clicks on them. Each point represents a Citizen Science campaign and when it is selected a pop-up window appears where the full dataset (data, metadata and photos) of the specific CS campaign is available (Figure 11). The displayed map offers dynamic tools with dragging & dropping and panning & zooming features (top left corner of the map) that are available to focus on a certain data subset if desired.

Data can be filtered using the "Filters" button located near the Zoom Controller that opens a modal window containing the filters that can be applied to the layers. This is particularly useful in case users would like to use only a subset of data that fulfils some conditions instead of having to deal with a full dataset that contains a considerable amount of data. The general filters include the selection of a time period (from date – to date) and the option to render data as time series, where the user can also specify the time-step interval and the visualization range. The filters available specifically for plastic litter data include Location name, Beach name, Plastic type, Surrounding type, Sediment type, Weather type and Contributor (Figure 12). After selection of filters, the already active layers will be reloaded to show only the selected data.

Figure 12. Filters available in the portal for Citizen Science plastic litter data.

Following the selection of layers and the application of filters, the users are able to create a report from the "Report" button on the top left of the map and download it (Figure 13). The report includes a table for each campaign with all the types of plastic litter according to EMODnet Chemistry J-list categories, also grouped as "Families". The "Families" are more general categories such as *plastic with undefined use* (e.g. bags, boxes and containers), *plastic used for food consumption* (bottles, packaging, cups, straws), *smoking litter* (cigarette butts, lighters), *fisheries* (nets, ropes), etc. The quantities (number of items) per plastic type and their % percentages as part of the total number of litter items are recorded for each campaign. The report includes two graphical charts for these data, a bar chart with quantitative data (%) per plastic type, and a pie chart with quantitative data (%) per plastic family.

Figure 13. Report created in the portal for the Citizen Science plastic litter data.

An "aggregated plastic litter map" is included at the beginning of each report in which pie charts with quantitative data per plastic family are georeferenced for all available locations (Figure 14). The users have the opportunity to identify if a general litter category is increased, reduced or absent from a location; for example, no litter related to fisheries (yellow colour) were present to the beaches located to the west of Heraklion city (Figure 14). At the end of each report an additional colour-coded table and a pie chart display the number of plastic litter collected by each contributor (i.e. school name), thus indicating the more active and dedicated participants throughout the project (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Aggregated litter map with litter "families" shown as pie charts for all locations.

Contributors Ranking

color	Contributor	Quantity
Red	Primary School Limenos Chersonissou	3324
Purple	Primary School Elias	2207
Orange	47th Primary School Heraklion	2044
Pink	Erasmus	1839
Yellow	Primary School Gouves	1772
Blue	Primary School Gouves	1221
Brown	Secondary Art School Heraklion	1044
Green	40th and 43rd Primary School Heraklion	974
Light Blue	A.T.A.X.T.O.I	895
Dark Blue	Nautilus summer school	438
Grey	Primary School Alikarnassou	373
Cyan	Special School Heraklion	277
Magenta	Secondary School Tylissou	272
Light Green	3rd Special School of Heraklion and 45th Primary School of Heraklion	243
White	Test contributor 2	0

Figure 15. Colour-coded table and pie chart displaying the number of plastic litter collected by different contributors.

The users can apply several filters in the available datasets and use the graphical tools offered in the produced reports to investigate specific hypothesis concerning certain locations, time periods or litter types. When a specific type of plastic litter is applied as a filter, such as the food packaging waste for example, additional informative graphs are included in the report. Therefore, Figure 16a concerns litter distribution in all areas within a specific year and indicates that during 2022 more plastic litter related to food packaging were present in the beaches Aquarium and Arina in comparison to other locations. Figure 16b presents a comparison between different years for all locations merged and indicates that plastic litter related to food packaging was very high during 2022 in comparison to all other years. Also, the users can create a graph summarising food packaging litter independently for all locations and years (Figure 16c), or a graph comparing all years for a selected location (Figure 16d).

These tools can be useful for monitoring plastic litter based on Citizen Science data and for supporting environmental awareness and engagement of the general public for their local environment. In addition, since a regular monitoring litter program is not usually applied to all regions in the country, these data can be also useful for local, regional and national authorities and stakeholders that need to design effective remediation measures within their territories.

Figure 16. Graphs produced within the portal's reports using the CS plastic litter data and following the application of the filter plastic type as "food packaging" for all locations and years.

VI. MONITORING OF PLASTIC LITTER BY FISHING VESSELS

Commercial fishing vessels belonging to the CNR-IRBIM AdriFOOS¹⁵ infrastructure have been used during the project as platforms for validation and demonstration of new generation sensors designed to be used on fishing vessels. The same infrastructure participated to CS initiatives, where professional fishermen acting on a voluntary basis in the Adriatic Sea collected and reported on plastic litter data. The AdriFOOS data center receives daily datasets of environmental parameters recorded along the water column and near the seabed, Global Positioning System tracks, catch quantity per haul, size of the species caught and meteorological information (Figure 17). A Microsoft SQL Server Compact Edition database is installed on a e-logbook, allowing storage of data directly entered by the fishermen through a suitable graphical user interface (GUI)¹⁶. A router ensuring bidirectional communication between the e-logbook and the CNR-IRBIM servers via cellular network is also installed on board and connect

HOME INFORMAZIONI TRACITTO SENSORI NELLA RETE SENSORI METEO RIASSUNTO PESCATO MAPPA PREVISIONALE

¹⁵ <https://>
¹⁶ Penna, obtained f
 15, 3513-

Accesso

Ciao Michela,

ESCI

Selezione barche

SB-02

Figure 17. Data transmitted to the AdriFOOS web viewer during one of the hauls where plastic litter was recorded.

More specifically, along with the regularly monitored data on commercial fish species noted in the AdriFOOS e-logbook, the professional fishermen were encouraged to record georeferenced and quantified data on plastic litter that they might encounter within their catch on board while their commercial fishing vessels were operating in the Adriatic Sea (Figure 18). These data are available in the NAUTILOS web data portal as a separate layer named “PlasticAdriFOOS”. Currently the dataset includes 4 entries (4 hauls in 3 days) (Figure 19). Given the nature of the observing platforms, the datasets are enriched with metadata including dates (start – end), coordinates (start – end), vessel ID, haul ID, type of plastic litter and quantity (number of items). Most items collected were fishing equipment, plastic bottles and containers.

Figure 18. Data entry for plastic litter into the GUI of the AdriFOOS e-logbook installed on board commercial fishing vessels.

Figure 19. Map with Citizen Science data on plastic litter collected by the AdriFOOS professional fishermen stored in the NAUTILOS portal.

VII. MONITORING OF PLASTIC LITTER WITH DRIFTERS

The Marine Litter Trackers (MLT) are low-cost smart-drifters equipped with a GSM real time tracking system, which were used in several Citizen Science initiatives involving local school students in Italy (Figure 20). More specifically, 9 experiments were performed within 2 years (2021-2022) and 46 drifters were released in total to study the dispersion of floating marine litter entering the sea from the mouth of the Arno and Magra rivers (Italy). The MLTs were tracked online by the students for about 10 days. The data collected were combined with disperssion models to better understand the dynamics of marine litter input into the seas by waterways in the Pelago Sanctuary area¹⁷. The plastic pollution Citizen Science data collected during these activities were stored in the NAUTILOS data portal (Figure 21) as a separate layer named “MiniDrifer” and they present the recorded georeferenced tracking lines of the MLTs, including metadata such as specific missions IDs, drifters codes and types.

Figure 20. Marine Litter Trackers used to study the dispersion of marine litter using open-source technology and a Citizen Science based approach.

Figure 21. Citizen Science data in the NAUTILOS portal presenting the georeferenced tracking lines of the Marine Litter Trackers.

VIII. MONITORING OF PLASTIC LITTER WITH DRONES

Citizen Science data on beach plastic litter were derived by students in Italy following the analysis of drone photos taken in the San Rossore Park (Pisa, Italy). The drone photos were collected from the beach Buca del Mare during 3 temporal periods (August, October, December) in year 2020. The recognition and classification of marine litter was performed during 2021 by High School students aged 16 to 18 years old, involved in the Pathways for Transversal Skills and Orientation (PCTO) scholastic project. In total, 122 students from 9 classes of 5 different Secondary Schools in Italy were invited to perform this virtual survey, based on a visual approach inside the GIS platform, with some semi-automatic tools helping them in AMD identification and measures. The students were trained in the use of GIS software and introduced to machine learning (ML) issues. They received supporting material prepared to help them during the remote survey including a video catalogue with images of marine litter taken from orthophotos and a video-recorded guide. The included images were extracted from orthophotos of the same geographic area of the survey, to allow operators to perform a better recognition of anthropogenic objects on the beach. In addition, a set of illustrated and video guides explaining the use of QGIS software for ML detection were provided.

The plastic litter categories used for the analysis of drone orthophotos were also archived according to the EMODnet Chemistry Thematic Lot n°4 categories (J code List), as was performed for the beach

plastic litter data in Crete (see Section II). An example of the obtained results for a coastal area of about 1 Km long is shown in Figure 22 in terms of items density (items/m²) during the 3 temporal periods considered, for the total number of items (left) and for the plastic bottle category (right). The highest number of litter type found within the total survey was for the categories of plastic bottles, buckets and large containers, as well as for pieces of unidentified plastic litter. These data have been uploaded in the NAUTILOS data portal as part of the layer “CS-Plastic” (Figure 23) enriched with the respective type of metadata (e.g. date, location, beach name, coordinates, beach dimensions, contributor, surround type, sediment).

Figure 22. Density of plastic items (items/m²) (colour-coded scale) for 3 temporal periods (T2, T4, T6) for total items (left) and for plastic bottles (right) found in the beach Buca del mare north area (top) and south area (down) following the analysis of drone photos.

Figure 23. Citizen Science data in NAUTILOS portal presenting the plastic litter identified using drone photos in the beach Buca del Mare of the San Rossore Park (Pisa, Italy) during 3 temporal periods (August, October, December) in year 2020.

IX. CLASSIFIER FOR THE ANNOTATION OF PLASTIC LITTER ON AERIAL DRONE IMAGES

An algorithm-based classifier, namely the Plastic Classifier, has been integrated in the NAUTILOS Citizen Science App for the automated detection and annotation of plastic litter in aerial drone images. This tool is based on artificial intelligence and can be used to assess the amount, types, and locations of plastic waste on images derived mainly from remote sensing operations. A model to classify the plastic litter on the captured images has been developed by DFKI and a simple interface to host the AI-model has been implemented in collaboration with CNR-ISTI. The classifier is integrated and managed through a dockerized container in the CS App and it can be accessed through a dedicated set of HTTP REST API. The software needed to operate the service and the machine learning libraries are written in PYTHON and installed on a Ubuntu based Linux system inside the virtual container. The DOCKER containerization method is a very popular system to deploy services and software on other machines with a minimum configuration needed by the host. Users can directly upload an aerial image to the classifier through the main page of the CS App. The classifier scales the original image and performs initially a rough classification separating waste from non-waste items, which is then followed by a fine classification separating the different plastic litter types. The classification procedure can be viewed through the CS App (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Detection and annotation of plastic litter in aerial images based on an algorithm classifier.

Photos of plastic waste collected by citizen scientists within the framework of NAUTILOS Citizen Science activities can be used as a data pool for the Plastic Classifier and form the basis for establishing the basic framework of an AI system which will be further trained and tested using the CS data (Figure 25). The result will be a graphical representation of the current distribution of plastic waste on maps, along with information on their composition (Figure 24). Analysis of these data can offer an insight to the identification of marine litter hotspots and to the type detection and quantification of plastic waste. In the long term, this concept could be used to monitor the main sources and distribution routes of plastic litter that is ending up in the aquatic environment, as well as for the coordination of any measures taken for the reduction of plastic pollution.

Figure 25. Image with plastic litter taken during a citizen science campaign in Crete (left) and its manual annotation (right) which will be used for the training of the AI model.

X. CONCLUSIONS

The Citizen Science activities that were performed within Task 12.2 aimed to create awareness and to engage the general public and the younger generations towards the more efficient protection of the marine environment. A change in attitude regarding the more sustainable production, use and recycling of plastic items can actually make a difference for future generations and for a healthier environment. The CS activities of Task 12.2 included beach cleaning campaigns for the collection and classification of plastic litter in which students and the general public participated, monitoring of plastics by professional fishermen, study of plastic litter dispersion models using smart drifters, monitoring of plastic litter using drone image analysis, and classification of plastic litter types using an AI algorithm integrated in the NAUTILOS CS App.

A significant number of CS datasets related to plastic pollution have been created and are now hosted in the NAUTILOS data portal. More specifically, 24 datasets of plastic litter from Cretan beaches (9 locations) were collected during 36 months in which 923 participants (mainly school students) collected 20,405 items of plastic litter. These data were collected under expert's supervision using specific protocols and 20 of the datasets have been already published in EMODnet catalogue (4 more are pending). Additional datasets on plastic litter that have been uploaded in the NAUTILOS web portal include: plastic litter collected during 4 hauls from commercial fishing vessels operating in the Adriatic Sea; tracking lines of 9 experiments using 46 smart drifters (Marine Litter Trackers) in Italy; and plastic

litter identified on drone photos using a GIS platform by 122 students during 3 seasonal periods in San Rossore Park (Italy).

All the data collected by the Citizen Scientists during these activities are available openly and freely in the NAUTILOS data portal. The data have been uploaded using the Citizen Science App (or its web browser version). The CS App is a powerful tool supporting Citizen Science data collection, sharing, analysis and visualisation and operates as a bridge towards the NAUTILOS data infrastructure (data portal). Filters applied on the available datasets can be used to produce reports with specialised graphs to investigate specific hypothesis concerning certain locations, time periods or litter types.

Data on marine plastic litter hold a significant value and attract interest from a wide range of stakeholders, including marine scientists, policymakers, local authorities, industry representatives, and environmental agencies across Europe and beyond. By providing new FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data—fully accessible through the NAUTILOS web portal and the EMODnet catalogue—this initiative plays a crucial role in supporting environmental assessments required by relevant EU Directives. It also ensures that the data remain discoverable, securely stored, and accessible over the long term and beyond the end of the project.